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What can we do with controlled vocabularies? The PIMMS story

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**British Atmospheric
Data Centre**

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Portable Infrastructure for the Metafor Metadata System

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/pimms/>

Common Information Model

We can talk about DataObjects collected together in any number of ways, stored in a particular medium

We reuse various ISO classes

Some concepts are shared

We can record the quality of things

We can talk about hierarchical ModelComponents with ModelProperties, some of which can be coupled together

A particular Activity uses a particular SoftwareComponent

We can define a GridSpec or some other geometry

We can talk about Simulations run in support of Experiments. Experiments consist of Requirements; Simulations conform to Requirements

Mind Maps

Mind maps are used to capture information requirements from domain experts and build a controlled vocabulary.

Python Parser

A python parser processes the XML files generated by the mind maps

```

<component name="Radiation">
  <definition status="missing">Definition of component type Radiation required</definition>
  <parameter name="RadiativeTimeStep" choice="keyboard">
    <definition status="missing">Definition of property name RadiativeTimeStep required</definition>
    <value format="numerical" name="time step" units="time units"/>
  </parameter>
  <parametergroup name="Longwave">
    <parameter name="SchemeType" choice="XOR">
      <definition status="missing">Definition of proper
      <value name="Wide-band model"/>
      <value name="Wide-band (Morcrette)"/>
      <value name="K-correlated"/>
      <value name="K-correlated (RRTM)"/>
      <value name="other"/>
    </parameter>
    <parameter name="Method" choice="XOR">
      <definition status="missing">Definition of proper
      <value name="Two stream"/>
      <value name="Layer interaction"/>
      <value name="other"/>
    </parameter>
    <parameter name="NumberOfSpectralIntervals" choice="keyboard">
      <definition status="missing">Definition of property name NumberOfSpectralIntervals required</definition>
      <value format="numerical" name=""/>
    </parameter>
  </parametergroup>

```


CMIP5 Questionnaire

<http://q.cmip5.ceda.ac.uk/>

All buttons and links above and in this column navigate away from this page. Save your work first!

Available Models

- GCM Template dup
 - + Aerosols
 - Atmosphere
 - + Atmos Convect Turbul Cloud
 - Atmos Dynamical Core
 - + Atmos Advection
 - + Atmos Key Properties
 - ... Atmos Orography And Waves
 - ... Atmos Radiation
 - + Atmospheric Chemistry
 - + Land Ice
 - + Land Surface
 - + Ocean
 - + Ocean Biogeo Chemistry
 - + Sea Ice

Component Atmos Advection

Please add details of any other relevant subcomponents of this component

Add Subcomponent

The button(s) in this box navigate to pages which further describe this

Short Name: (type: AtmosAdvection)

Implemented: Untick the box if there is no representation of AtmosAdvection in your model.

Long Name:

Responsible Parties (Use the parties tab to add more choices here):

Contact:

Principal Investigator:

Funder:

Copy Parties to sub-components

Component Attributes

In this section enter the grid and other parameters and attributes associated with this component .

Grid

Please select an appropriate grid from those you have described using the grid tab

Grid: Copy Grid to sub-components

General Attributes

You can enter attributes or parameters here if you wish (to enter more than one, you need to save them one at a time - using the button below - to get blank entry forms).

Name	Value	Delete
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Tracers

<i>SchemeName</i>	Choose one of:	<input type="text" value="other"/>
<i>SchemeType</i>	Choose one of:	<input type="text" value="semi-Lagrangian"/>
<i>ConservedQuantities</i>	Enter string value:	<input type="text"/>
<i>ConservationMethod</i>	Choose one or more of:	<input type="text" value="conservation fixer"/>

You can enter additional attributes or parameters here if you wish (to enter more than one, you need to save them one at a time - using the button below to get blank entry forms).

Name	Value	Delete
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Model: HadCM3

 Overview Information

shortName	HadCM3
longName	HadCM3 (2000) atmosphere: HadAM3 (N48L19); ocean: HadOM (lat: 1.25 lon: 1.25 L20); land-surface/vegetation: MOSES1;
description	HadCM3 is a coupled atmosphere-ocean GCM developed at the Hadley Centre and described by Gordon et al. (2000). It has a stable control climatology and does not use flux adjustment. The climate component represented the model used by the Hadley Centre to provide input for the IPCC Third and Fourth Assessment Reports. The atmosphere and ocean are coupled once per day. The atmospheric model is run with fixed SSTs through the day and the various forcing fluxes are accumulated each atmospheric model time step. At the end of the day these fluxes are passed to the ocean model which is then integrated forwards in time. The updated SSTs and sea ice extents are then passed back to the atmospheric model. As there are six ocean grid points to every atmospheric grid point interpolation and/or averaging is used to transfer fields between the two grids conserved.
type	model

 Responsible Parties

Geoscientific Model Development
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Simulating the mid-Pliocene climate with the MIROC general circulation model: experimental design and initial results

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Abstract. Recently, PlioMIP (Pliocene Model Intercomparison Project) was established to assess the ability of various climate models to simulate the mid-Pliocene warm period (mPWP), 3.3–3.0 million years ago. We use MIROC4m, a fully coupled atmosphere-ocean general circulation model (AOGCM), and its atmospheric component alone to simulate the mPWP, utilizing up-to-date data sets designated in PlioMIP as boundary conditions and adhering to the protocols outlined. In this paper, a brief description of the model is given, followed by an explanation of the experimental design and implementation of the boundary conditions, such as topography and sea surface temperature. Initial results show increases of approximately 10°C in the zonal mean surface air temperature at high latitudes accompanied by a decrease in the equator-to-pole temperature gradient. Temperatures in the tropical regions increase more in the AOGCM. However, warming of the AOGCM sea surface in parts of the northern North Atlantic Ocean and Nordic Seas is less than that suggested by proxy data. An investigation of the model-data discrepancies and further model intercomparison studies can lead to a better understanding of the mid-Pliocene climate and of its role in assessing future climate change.

Final Revised Paper (PDF, 3048 KB) Discussion Paper (GMDD) Special Issue

Citation: Chan, W.-L., Abe-Ouchi, A., and Ohgaito, R.: Simulating the mid-Pliocene climate with the MIROC general circulation model: experimental design and initial results, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 4, 1035-1049, doi:10.5194/gmd-4-1035-2011, 2011. Bibtex EndNote Reference Manager XML

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Numerical uncertainty at mesoscale in a Lagrangian model in complex terrain

ChemicalTagger is an open-source tool that uses OSCAR4 and NLP techniques for tagging and parsing experimental sections in the chemistry literature.

ChemicalTagger

University of Cambridge > Department of Chemistry > Unilever Centre for Molecular Science Informatics

To a stirred solution of 4-hydroxypiperidine (0.97 g, CD CD9.60NN-AMOUNTmmol) in anhydrous dimethylformamide (20 mL) at 0 °C was added 1-(bromomethyl)-4-methoxybenzene (1.93 g, CD CD9.60NN-AMOUNTmmol) and triethylamine (2.16 g, CD CD21.4NN-AMOUNTmmol) . The reaction mixture was then warmed to room temperature and stirred overnight . After this time the mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the resulting residue was dissolved in ethyl acetate (40 mL) , washed with water (20 mL) and brine (20 mL) before being dried over sodium sulfate . The drying agent was filtered off and the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure . The residue obtained was purified by flash chromatography (silica gel , 0-5 % methanol / methylene chloride) to afford 1-(4-methoxybenzyl)piperidin-4-ol as a brown oil (1.70 g, 80 %) .

Conditions:

TimePhrase

Molecules:

Other

Phrases:

PrepPhrase NounPhrase ParentheticalPhrase UnmatchedPhrase AcronymPhrase VerbPhrase

Quantitative_Terms:

Quantity

Chemical Tagger and PIMMS

- xslt transform has been written to allow the Metafor atmosphere controlled vocabulary to be used by chemical tagger
- Chemical tagger software then parsed a GMD abstract and experiment description looking for Metafor Controlled Vocabularies
- the software identified many useful phrases

```
NN-MODEL template is called. With a value of :  
generalcirculationmodel(AOGCM)  
With domain (from preceding-sibling): atmosphere-ocean
```

```
ResolutionPhrase: With a value of :  
HorizontalresolutionsettoT42,  
correspondingroughlytoagridsizeof2.8°
```

```
Vertical Resolution: 20verticalslevels
```

```
VERTICAL DETAILS: and the height of the model top  
isapproximately 30km .
```

Chemical Tagger and PIMMS

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/pimms/wiki/wp1/hangoutMeetings/20120227>

NN-MODEL template is called.

With a value of : `oceangeneralcirculationmodel(OGCM)`

NN-MODEL With domain: `ocean`

Equation Type : `Primitive`

Equation Type : `hydrostatic`

Equation Type : `Boussinesq`

ResolutionPhrase: With a value of : `zonalresolution
isfixedat1.40625°1.40625°`

Horizontal Grid with value: `256equallyspacedgridpoints`

Horizontal Grid with value: `192gridpoints`

Vertical Resolution: `43verticallevels`

VERTICAL DETAILS: , `thetop8ofwhich areiso-coordinates` .

CIM Document Viewer

<http://zonda5.badc.rl.ac.uk/site/public/tools>

 Climate Science Metadata Standards
metafor Common Information Model

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TOOLS - VIEWER

Open a valid CIM XML file and click View. A user friendly view will be generated and displayed.

CIM XML File:

[Open](#)

[View](#)

Harvested Metadata vs Documented Metadata

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/pimms/blog/>

CIM was designed to be populated by modellers with the (probably over simplistic) assumption that if something isn't in the CIM document then it either isn't in the model or isn't relevant. But CIM documents created by harvesting information from papers will naturally not cover everything about a model, so missing info doesn't mean that those things weren't included/aren't relevant.

PIMMS will need to describe different protocols for interpreting CIM documents depending on how they were created, but we will also want to ensure that that CIM accounts for missing data more intelligently in future releases.

In essence the difference between journal article descriptions and metadata documentation is Narrative. Journal articles need to tell a story so the information they include is only that which is relevant to the narrative, whereas metadata documentation is an attempt to include as much as possible across the board. The general nature of metadata documentation is probably why it has historically been perceived as such a boring task to complete.

PIMMS will make metadata documentation more fun by bringing back the Narrative, once PIMMS is established at an institution users will be able to create generalised metadata having only described those things that are relevant to the story of their experiment.